

Equitable Resolving Domination in Product of Two Graphs

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Abstract— For an ordered subset $W = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k$ of vertices and a vertex v in a connected graph G , the resolving vector of v with respect to W is the ordered k -tuple $r(v|W) = (d(v, w_1), d(v, w_2), \dots, d(v, w_k))$, where $d(x, y)$ represents the distance between the vertices x and y in G . The set W is a resolving set for G if every two distinct vertices of G have distinct resolving vector with respect to W . The minimum cardinality of a resolving set is called the metric dimension of G , denoted by $dim(G)$. A dominating set D is called equitable if for every vertex $v \in V(G) - D$, there exists a vertex $u \in D$ such that $uv \in E(G)$ and $|deg(u) - deg(v)|$ is atmost 1. A dominating set which is both equitable as well as resolving is called an equitable resolving dominating set. The minimum cardinality of an equitable resolving dominating set is called an equitable resolving domination number of G which is denoted by $\gamma_{rs}^e(G)$. In this paper we investigate exact values of equitable resolving domination number in cartesian product as well as strong product of two graphs. We also obtain the Vizing's conjecture type results in the context of γ_{rs}^e .

Keywords— Dominating set, equitable dominating set, resolving dominating set, equitable resolving dominating set, cartesian product of graphs, strong product of graphs

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I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of domination has received a considerable attention as one of the emerging fields of research in graph theory due to its applications for the study of real life situations. A subset D of vertex set $V(G)$ in a graph G is called a dominating set if every vertex $v \in V(G)$ is either an element of D or it is adjacent to an element of D . If no proper subset $D' \subset D$ is a dominating set then dominating set D is called a minimal dominating set. The domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma(G)$ is defined as the minimum cardinality of a dominating set of G and the corresponding dominating set is called γ - set of G .

Variety of dominating sets are available in the existing literature. These variants are introduced by identifying one or more characteristics of elements of vertex subset or edge subset. A brief account on dominating set and related concepts can be found in Haynes *et al* [4,5]. One such variant is equitable domination. A dominating set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is called an equitable dominating set if for every vertex $v \in V(G) - D$, there exists a vertex $u \in D$ such that $uv \in E(G)$ and $|deg(u) - deg(v)| \leq 1$. The minimum cardinality of an equitable dominating set is called an equitable domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma^e(G)$. This concept was conceived by Swaminathan and Dharmalingam [10].

The distance $d(u, v)$ between two vertices in G is the length of the shortest path between u and v in G . Let $W = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k$ be an ordered subset of $V(G)$ and let $v \in V(G)$, then the k -vector $(d(v, w_1), d(v, w_2), \dots, d(v, w_k))$ is called the resolving vector of v with respect to W and is denoted by $r(v|W)$. The set W is called a resolving set of G if $r(u|W) \neq r(v|W)$ for any two distinct vertices u and v . The minimum cardinality of a resolving set of G is called the metric dimension of G and is denoted by $dim(G)$. The concept of resolving set was independently discovered by Harary and Melter [3] who used the terms resolving set and metric dimension and by Slater [9] who used the terms locating set and location number. A set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is called a resolving dominating set if it is resolving and dominating both. The minimum cardinality of a resolving dominating set is called a resolving domination number of G , denoted by $\gamma_{rs}(G)$. The concept of resolving domination was introduced by Chartrand *et al.* [1].

II. PRELIMINERIES

Motivated by the concepts of equitable domination and resolving domination, a new concept of equitable resolving domination in graphs is recently introduced by Vaidya and Kelaiya [11] and further explored by the same authors in [12, 13].

Definition 2.1. [11] *A dominating set which is both equitable and resolving is called an equitable resolving dominating set.*

Definition 2.2. [11] *The equitable resolving domination number of G is the minimum cardinality of an equitable resolving dominating set of G which is denoted by $\gamma_{rs}^e(G)$.*

Definition 2.3. *The cartesian product $G \square H$ of two graphs $G = (V(G), E(G))$ and $H = (V(H), E(H))$, is the graph with vertex set $V(G \square H) = \{(u, v) / u \in V(G) \text{ and } v \in V(H)\}$ and edge set $E(G \square H) = \{(u, v)(u', v') / u = u' \text{ and } vv' \in E(H) \text{ or } uu' \in E(G) \text{ and } v = v'\}$.*

Definition 2.4. *An n -dimensional grid is a cartesian product of paths $P_{m_1} \square P_{m_2} \square \dots \square P_{m_n}$.*

Throughout the paper, we consider finite, simple, connected and undirected graph G with the vertex set $V(G)$ and the edge set $E(G)$. For standard terminology and notation in graph theory we rely upon West [15] while for any undefined term related to theory of domination we refer to Haynes *et al.* [4]. We state the following existing results for our ready reference.

Theorem 2.5. [11] *Let G be a connected graph, then*

$$\max\{\gamma^e(G), \dim(G)\} \leq \gamma_{rs}^e(G) \leq \gamma^e(G) + \dim(G).$$

Theorem 2.6. [11] *If G is a regular or $(k, k + 1)$ biregular graph, for $k > 0$ then $\gamma_{rs}(G) = \gamma_{rs}^e(G)$.*

Theorem 2.7. [6] *The metric dimension of an n -dimensional grid ($n \geq 2$) is n .*

Lemma 2.8. [2] *For every graph G and for all $n \geq 1$,*

$$\dim(K_n \square G) \leq \max\{n - 1, 2 \cdot \dim(G)\}$$

Theorem 2.9. [2]

$$\dim(P_n \square C_m) = \begin{cases} 2 & ; \text{ if } m \text{ is odd} \\ 3 & ; \text{ if } m \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2.10. [7]

$$\gamma(P_n \square C_m) = \begin{cases} \left\lceil \frac{3n}{4} \right\rceil & ; \text{ if } m = 3 \text{ and } n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{4} \\ n & ; \text{ if } m = 4 \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2.11. [2]

$$\dim(C_n \square C_m) = \begin{cases} 3 & ; \text{if } m \text{ or } n \text{ is odd} \\ 4 & ; \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.12. The strong product $G \boxtimes H$ of two graphs $G = (V(G), E(G))$ and $H = (V(H), E(H))$, is the graph with vertex set $V(G \boxtimes H) = \{(u, v)/u \in V(G) \text{ and } v \in V(H)\}$ and edge set $E(G \boxtimes H) = \{(u, v)(u', v')/u = u' \text{ and } vv' \in E(H) \text{ or } uu' \in E(G) \text{ and } v = v' \text{ or } uu' \in E(G) \text{ and } vv' \in E(H)\}$.

Theorem 2.13. [8] Let G and H be two connected graphs of order $n_1 \geq 2$ and n_2 , respectively. Then

$$\dim(G \boxtimes H) \leq n_1 \cdot \dim(H) + n_2 \cdot \dim(G) - \dim(G) \cdot \dim(H)$$

Theorem 2.14. [8] For all $m, n \geq 3$,

$$\dim(K_m \boxtimes K_n) = m \cdot n - 1$$

Theorem 2.15. [8] For all $n_1 \geq 2$ and $n_2 \geq 4$,

$$\dim(K_{n_1} \boxtimes C_{n_2}) = n_2(n_1 - 1)$$

III. EQUITABLE RESOLVING DOMINATION IN CARTESIAN PRODUCT OF TWO GRAPHS

We recall the Definition 2.3. of cartesian product of two graphs and prove the following results.

Theorem 3.1. For every graph G with order $n \geq 3$ and for all $m \geq 3$,

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \square G) \leq \gamma^e(K_m \square G) + \max\{m - 1, 2 \cdot \dim(G)\}$$

Proof. From Theorem 2.5, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \square G) \leq \gamma^e(K_m \square G) + \dim(K_m \square G)$. Also, from Lemma 2.8 we have $\dim(K_m \square G) \leq \max\{m - 1, 2 \cdot \dim(G)\}$. Thus, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \square G) \leq \gamma^e(K_m \square G) + \max\{m - 1, 2 \cdot \dim(G)\}$. ■

Theorem 3.2. For every regular graph G with order $n \geq 3$ and for all $m \geq 3$,

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \square G) = \gamma_{rs}(K_m \square G)$$

Proof. The graph K_m is $m - 1$ regular graph and consider G as d regular graph then it is clear that the cartesian product $K_m \square G$ is an $m - 1 + d$ regular graph. Hence, by Theorem 2.6, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \square G) = \gamma_{rs}(K_m \square G)$. ■

Theorem 3.3.

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(P_n \square P_m) = \begin{cases} 3 & ; \text{for } P_2 \square P_3, P_3 \square P_2 \\ \gamma(P_n \square P_m) & ; \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Proof.

Case 1. From Theorem 2.7, $\dim(P_2 \square P_3) = \dim(P_3 \square P_2) = 2$. It is easy to observe that degree of the vertices in $P_2 \square P_3$ and $P_3 \square P_2$ is either 2 or 3. Also, no set of cardinality 2 is both a resolving set as well

as dominating set. Since, any super set of resolving set is also a resolving set we need atleast three vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. $\gamma_{rs}^e(P_2 \square P_3) = \gamma_{rs}^e(P_3 \square P_2) = 3$.

Case 2. From Theorem 2.7, $dim(P_n \square P_m) = 2$. Also, any super set of a resolving set is also a resolving set. Moreover, degree of the vertices in $P_n \square P_m$ is 2,3 and 4. Hence, the number of vertices we need to dominate all the vertices of $P_n \square P_m$ is itself forms a dominating set as well as equitable resolving dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{rs}^e(P_n \square P_m) = \gamma(P_n \square P_m)$. ■

Theorem 3.4.

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(P_n \square C_m) = \begin{cases} 3 & ; \text{ for } P_2 \square C_3, P_2 \square C_4 \\ \gamma(P_n \square C_m) & ; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Proof.

Case 1. From Theorem 2.9, $dim(P_2 \square C_3) = 2$. Also, degree of the vertices in $P_2 \square C_3$ is 3. Also, from Theorem 2.10, $\gamma(P_2 \square C_3) = 2$. Moreover, it can be verified that no set of cardinality 2 is both a resolving set as well as dominating set. Since, any super set of resolving set is also a resolving set. We need atleast three vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. $\gamma_{rs}^e(P_2 \square C_3) = 3$.

From Theorem 2.9, $dim(P_2 \square C_4) = 3$. Also, degree of the vertices in $P_2 \square C_4$ is 3 and from Theorem 2.10, $\gamma(P_2 \square C_4) = 2$. Moreover, no set of cardinality 2 is a resolving set. Therefore, we need atleast three vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{rs}^e(P_2 \square C_4) = 3$.

Case 2. From Theorem 2.9, $dim(P_n \square C_m) = 2$ or 3. Also, any super set of a resolving set is also a resolving set. Moreover, degree of the vertices in $P_n \square C_m$ is 2,3 and 4. Hence, the number of vertices we need to dominate all the vertices of $P_n \square C_m$ is itself forms a dominating set as well as equitable resolving dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{rs}^e(P_n \square C_m) = \gamma(P_n \square C_m)$. ■

Theorem 3.5.

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(C_n \square C_m) = \begin{cases} 4 & ; \text{ for } C_3 \square C_3, C_4 \square C_3, C_3 \square C_4 \\ 5 & ; \text{ for } C_4 \square C_4 \\ \gamma(C_n \square C_m) & ; \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Proof.

Case 1. From Theorem 2.11, $dim(C_3 \square C_3) = 4$. Also, degree of the vertices in $C_3 \square C_3$ is 4. Also, no set of cardinality 3 is resolving set. While $\gamma(C_3 \square C_3) = 3$ but for resolving set we need atleast four vertices. $\gamma_{rs}^e(C_3 \square C_3) = 4$.

From Theorem 2.11, $dim(C_4 \square C_3) = dim(C_3 \square C_4) = 3$. Also, degree of the vertices in $C_4 \square C_3$ and $C_3 \square C_4$ is 4. Moreover, no set of cardinality 3 is both a resolving set as well as dominating set. Since, any super set of resolving set is also a resolving set we need atleast four vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. $\gamma_{rs}^e(C_4 \square C_3) = \gamma_{rs}^e(C_3 \square C_4) = 3$.

Case 2. From Theorem 2.11, $dim(C_4 \square C_4) = 4$. Also, degree of the vertices in $C_4 \square C_4$ is 4. Moreover, no set of cardinality 4 is both a resolving set as well as dominating. Since, any super set of resolving set is also a resolving set we need atleast five vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. $\gamma_{rs}^e(C_4 \square C_4) = 5$.

Case 3. From Theorem 2.11, $dim(C_n \square C_m) = 3$ or 4. Also, any super set of a resolving set is also a resolving set. Moreover, C_n is a 2- regular graph. Therefore, $C_n \square C_m$ is a 4- regular graph. Hence, the number of vertices we need to dominate all the vertices of $C_n \square C_m$ is itself forms a dominating set as well as equitable resolving dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{rs}^e(C_n \square C_m) = \gamma(C_n \square C_m)$. ■

IV. EQUITABLE RESOLVING DOMINATION IN STRONG PRODUCT OF TWO GRAPHS

We recall the Definition 2.12. of strong product of two graphs and prove the following results.

Theorem 4.1. For every regular graph G with order $n \geq 3$ and for all $m \geq 3$,

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes G) = \dim(K_m \boxtimes G)$$

Proof. Graph K_m is a regular graph and G is also regular graph. Therefore $K_m \boxtimes G$ is also a regular graph. From Theorem 2.6, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes G) = \gamma_{rs}(K_m \boxtimes G)$. Since, $K_m \boxtimes G$ is a regular graph we need atleast $\dim(K_m \boxtimes G)$ vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes G) = \dim(K_m \boxtimes G)$. ■

Corollary 4.2. For all $m, n \geq 3$,

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes K_n) = \dim(K_m \boxtimes K_n) = m \cdot n - 1$$

Proof. Here K_n is a regular graph. Hence, from Theorem 4.1 and 2.14, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes K_n) = \dim(K_m \boxtimes K_n) = m \cdot n - 1$. ■

Corollary 4.3. For all $m \geq 3$ and $n \geq 4$,

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes C_n) = \dim(K_m \boxtimes C_n) = n(m - 1)$$

Proof. Here C_n is a regular graph. Hence, from Theorem 4.1 and 2.15, $\gamma_{rs}^e(K_m \boxtimes C_n) = \dim(K_m \boxtimes C_n) = n(m - 1)$. ■

Theorem 4.4. For all $m, n \geq 3$,

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(C_m \boxtimes C_n) = \dim(C_m \boxtimes C_n)$$

Proof. Since C_m is a regular graph $C_m \boxtimes C_n$ is also a regular graph. From Theorem 2.6, $\gamma_{rs}^e(C_m \boxtimes C_n) = \gamma_{rs}(C_m \boxtimes C_n)$. Since, $C_m \boxtimes C_n$ is a regular graph we need atleast $\dim(C_m \boxtimes C_n)$ vertices to form an equitable resolving dominating set. Hence, $\gamma_{rs}^e(C_m \boxtimes C_n) = \dim(C_m \boxtimes C_n)$. ■

VIZING'S CONJECTURE

The Vizing's conjecture[14] for cartesian product of two graphs G and H is stated as,

$$\gamma(G \square H) \geq \gamma(G) \cdot \gamma(H)$$

Vizing also observed the upper bound for the domination number of cartesian product of two graphs, which is,

$$\gamma(G \square H) \leq \min\{\gamma(G)|V(H)|, \gamma(H)|V(G)|\}$$

We explore the Vizing's conjecture in the context of strong product of two graphs G and H and establish the following result.

Theorem 4.5. Let G and H be two connected graphs of order $n_2 \geq n_1 \geq 2$, respectively. Then

$$\gamma_{rs}^e(G \boxtimes H) \leq \gamma^e(G \boxtimes H) + n_1 \cdot \dim(H) + n_2 \cdot \dim(G) - \dim(G) \cdot \dim(H)$$

Proof. From Theorem 2.5, $\gamma_{rs}^e(G \boxtimes H) \leq \gamma^e(G \boxtimes H) + \dim(G \boxtimes H)$. Also, from Theorem 2.13, we have $\dim(G \boxtimes H) \leq n_1 \cdot \dim(H) + n_2 \cdot \dim(G) - \dim(G) \cdot \dim(H)$. Thus, $\gamma_{rs}^e(G \boxtimes H) \leq \gamma^e(G \boxtimes H) + n_1 \cdot \dim(H) + n_2 \cdot \dim(G) - \dim(G) \cdot \dim(H)$. ■

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have derived some general results on the concept of equitable resolving domination in product of graphs which is recently introduced by Vaidya and Kelaiya [12] and obtained the equitable resolving domination number for the graphs obtained by cartesian product and strong product of two graphs. The Vizing's conjecture type results have been also proved.

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